

Impact of Globalization on the Poor

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Abstract:

This paper identifies and discusses the effects of globalization on poverty. Globalization affects poverty both negatively and positively. The characteristics of globalization are discussed. Poverty is defined in detail and it has brought a lot of disadvantages to the societies. It leads to people feeling themselves inferior than others, left behind and rejected. They have to struggle hard to survive. Globalization brings economic growth but this economic growth does not benefit everyone equally. It increases inequality and poverty in the less developed countries. It has increased costs which are difficult to bear for the poor the increase in trade and investment has reduced the capita income. The technological advancements occurred has benefits but they have many negative effects also. They have led to downsizing of employees leading to unemployment and poverty

Keywords: Globalization

INTRODUCTION

Globalization is a very vast term. It covers every aspect. It has many different definitions. Globalization is the growing integration of economies and societies around the world. It ranges from the issues of trade and services, movement of capital, growth and poverty of the world population, international migration to easier transportation and communication around the world. It is a complex process that affects many lives and above all, increased economic interdependence among countries. Here globalization is viewed purely in its economic dimensions – defined as increasing integration of a national economy with the world economy through exchange of goods and services, capital flows, technology, information, and labour migration. Some of the characteristics of globalization are:

1- **Borderless :**

Globalization is about an increasingly borderless world and its societal consequences. The causes of globalization are technological, economic and ideological.

2- **Free Trade:**

Free trade between countries; absence of excessive governmental control over trade;

3- **Globalization of Economic Activities:**

Control of economic activities by domestic market and international market; coordination of national economy and world economy;

4- **Connectivity:**

Localities being connected with the world by breaking national boundaries; forging of links between one society and another, and between one country and another through international transmission of knowledge, literature, technology, culture and information.

Globalization has both pros and cons .for some its very beneficial and for other it has become a hazard.

Poverty is defined as the state of being extremely poor. Poverty is said to exist when people lack the means to satisfy their basic needs. In this context, the identification of poor people first requires a determination of what constitutes basic needs. These may be defined as narrowly as those necessary for survival or as broadly as those reflecting the prevailing standard of living in the community. It does not only mean hunger. It is associated with poor health, low levels of education or skills, an inability or an unwillingness to work, high rates of disruptive

or disorderly behavior and improvidence. Our country is facing a high level of poverty which is the basic hurdle in the development of our country. There are a lot of disadvantages which result due to poverty and they are :

1- Overpopulation:

Overpopulation increases poverty. The resources are already scarce and with increasing population these resources will have to be divided among more people hence increasing poverty.

2- Unequal distribution of wealth and income:

The income and resources are unequally distributed in our society. The rich are getting richer and the poor poorer.

3- Lack of education:

Education has long been a problem in society, because the lack of this essential tool of survival does not allow for growth of any sort. It is a known fact that the risk of poverty usually decreases as people get more schooling. Poor education can be either a cause of poverty or an effect. Young people who drop out of school may be poor because they lack the required skills needed to get good jobs, therefore adding to a system that forces them to only be able to live in low income, economically starving areas. Moreover, education is a basic requirement in order to climb a hierarchy of income in our society, so uneducated people are forced too become content with their surroundings.

4- Disease :

When a community has a high disease rate , absenteeism is high, productivity is low, and less wealth is created. Apart from the misery, discomfort and death that results from disease, it is also a major factor in poverty in a community. Being well not only helps the individuals who are healthy, it contributes to the eradication of poverty in the community.

5- Unemployment:

One of the biggest reasons of poverty in Pakistan is unemployment. People are not getting jobs and the ones who are getting are not upto their standards so even these unsatisfied employees consider them unemployed. There are no jobs in the market and highly educated and skilled people ar left jobless and without any earning this have increased poverty level in the country.

6- Power crisis :

The power crisis has also increased poverty .the power shortage and lack of resources have forced industries to implement the downsizing policy. They are dismissing people to meet their expenditures. The people become jobless and unpaid which increase poverty.

7- Increasing inflation:

Due to rising inflation things are getting beyond the reach of people and their incomes have become insufficient as compared to the expenses.. they are not even able to satisfy their basic needs of life . all this leads to further poverty.

8- Dependency :

Dependency results from being on the receiving end of charity. In the short run, as after a disaster, that charity may be essential for survival. In the long run, that charity can contribute to the possible demise of the recipient and certainly to ongoing poverty.

9- Natural disasters :

Natural disasters such as hurricanes and earthquakes have devastated communities throughout the world. Developing countries often suffer much more extensive and acute crises at the hands of natural disasters, because limited resources inhibit the construction of adequate housing, infrastructure, and mechanisms for responding to crises.

EFFECTS OF POVERTY

Poverty is a major cause of social tensions and threatens to divide a nation because of the issue of inequalities, in particular income inequality. This happens when wealth in a country is poorly distributed among citizens. In other words, when tiny minority has all the money.

The effects of poverty are serious. Children who grow up in poverty suffer more persistent, frequent, and severe health problems than do children who grow up under better financial circumstances.

- Many infants born into poverty have a low birth weight, which is associated with many preventable mental and physical disabilities. Not only are these poor infants more likely to be irritable or sickly, they are also more likely to die before their first birthday.
- Children raised in poverty tend to miss school more often because of illness. These children also have a much higher rate of accidents than do other children, and they are twice as likely to have impaired vision and hearing, iron deficiency anemia, and higher than normal levels of lead in the blood, which can impair brain function.

Levels of stress in the family have also been shown to correlate with economic circumstances. Studies during economic recessions indicate that job loss and subsequent poverty are associated with violence in families, including child and elder abuse. Poor families experience much more stress than middle-class families. Besides financial uncertainty, these families are more likely to be exposed to series of negative events including illness, depression, eviction, job loss, criminal victimization, and family death. Parents who experience hard economic times may become excessively punitive and erratic, issuing demands backed by insults, threats, and corporal punishment.

Homelessness, or extreme poverty, carries with it a particularly strong set of risks for families, especially children. Compared to children living in poverty but having homes, homeless children are less likely to receive proper nutrition and immunization. Hence, they experience more health problems. Homeless women experience higher rates of low-birth-weight babies, miscarriages, and infant mortality, probably due to not having access to adequate prenatal care for their babies. Homeless families experience even greater life stress than other families, including increased disruption in work, school, family relationships, and friendships.

CHANNELS LINKING GLOBALIZATION TO POVERTY

What are the transmission mechanisms through which the process of globalization affects poverty directly and indirectly? The first and most important of these mechanisms is the growth–inequality–poverty channel. Other channels operate, respectively, through changes in relative prices of factors of production (labour and capital) and commodities, movements of capital and labour migration across borders, the nature of technological change and technological diffusion, the impact of globalization on volatility and vulnerability, the worldwide flow of information, global disinflation, and institutions. Globalization affects poverty through many different channels: growth, inequality, international capital movements and labour migration, technology, information, vulnerability, and institutions

When we here the term globalization, a very ideal view of it comes to our mind in which the markets are working properly, capital and technology is flowing freely, knowledge is easily accessible to people and everyone has an equal chance to participate in the market. But is it really so?

Some say that globalization reduces poverty others say that it increases poverty. The people in favor of globalization say that Globalization provides a strong potential for a major reduction in poverty in the

developing world because it creates an environment conducive to faster economic growth and transmission of knowledge. However, structural factors and policies within the world economy and national economies have impeded the full transmission of the benefits of the various channels of globalization for poverty reduction. It has opened the free markets and reduced the barriers to trade and investment due to which the poor have been able to improve their positions. Globalization aids economic growth and rapid economic growth of the right pattern does help alleviate poverty.

The people against globalization or anti globalists say that This process of globalisation is one of the most critical developments affecting the evolution of national economies. Globalization offers participating countries new opportunities for accelerating growth and development but, at the same time, it also poses challenges to, and imposes constraints on policy makers in the management of national, regional and global economic systems. While the opportunities offered by globalization can be large, a question is often raised as to whether the actual distribution of gains is fair, in particular, whether the poor benefit less than proportionately from globalization – and could under some circumstances actually be hurt by it.

The benefits of globalization are not equally distributed and tend to be concentrated among a relatively small number of countries, particularly the more advanced ones. The poorest countries such as the least developed countries in Africa have not been able to sufficiently harvest the benefits of globalization. Second, most efforts have been placed in facilitating free trade flows, particularly in products which are of importance to the developed countries, as part of the globalization process. Other dimensions of globalization like labor market standards, the environment, sustainable development and poverty alleviation has received much less attention. Third globalization has also led to an increased vulnerability among many countries to international economic conditions.

The risks and costs brought about by globalization can be significant for fragile developing economies and the world's poor. The downside of globalization is most vividly epitomized at times of periodical global financial and economic crises. The costs of the repeated crises associated with economic and financial globalization appear to have been borne overwhelmingly by the developing world, and often disproportionately so by the poor who are the most vulnerable. On the other hand, benefits from globalization in booming times are not necessarily shared widely and equally in the global community. The fear that the poor have been by-passed or actually hurt by globalization was highlighted by the finding from a number of studies, emerging recently, which explicitly examined the extent of, and changes in inequality of the world income distribution as it evolved during the heyday of the globalization era

Many of these studies point towards a continuing high inequality in the world income distribution and limited-if not a lack of - convergence among participating national economies and across regions as globalization has proceeded. Poverty, as measured by the headcount ratio has fallen world-wide except in Sub Saharan Africa where it continues to rise.

Developing countries are in need of concrete guidelines on the appropriate social, market and political instruments and delivery mechanisms that can bridge the micro world of the poor and the macro world of national economies and on appropriate sequencing of instruments and mechanism to ensure fast and optimal benefits for the rural poor

The trickle-down effect from growth to poverty reduction is based on the assumption that economic growth is distribution neutral or, if not, distribution improving. In recent years numerous theoretical and empirical studies have dealt with the argument of inequality to growth, growth to inequality and growth to poverty relationships developed.

Economic globalization is found to negatively impact poverty. We can say that globalization reduces poverty in the long-run, generates employment opportunities but worsens inequality. It is purported that trade liberalization aspect of globalization is a necessary but not sufficient condition for growth. There are other mediating factors which affect the growth of the economy ranging from political and institutional framework to historical trend in macroeconomic variables included but not limited to population, inflation, investment and government spending dynamics.

Globalization has been associated with rising inequality, and that the poor do not always share in the gains from trade. The poor in countries with an abundance of unskilled labor do not always gain from trade reform. The poor are more likely to share in the gains from globalization when workers enjoy maximum mobility, especially from contracting economic sectors into expanding sectors. Gains likewise arise when poor farmers have access to credit and technical know-how, when poor farmers have such social safety nets as income support and when food aid is well targeted.

The export growth and incoming foreign investment have reduced poverty everywhere from Mexico to India to Poland. Yet at the same time currency crises can cripple the poor.

Globalization produces both winners and losers among the poor. In Mexico, for example, small and medium corn growers saw their incomes halved in the 1990s, while larger corn growers prospered. In other countries, poor workers in exporting sectors or in sectors with foreign investment gained from trade and investment reforms, while poverty rates increased in previously protected areas that were exposed to import competition. Even within a country, a trade reform may hurt rural agricultural producers and benefit rural or urban consumers of those farmers' products.

Economic globalization is leading to a concentration of the seed industry, the increased use of pesticides, and, finally, increased debt. Capital-intensive, corporate-controlled agriculture is being spread into regions where peasants are poor but, until now, have been self-sufficient in food. In the regions where industrial agriculture has been introduced through globalization, higher costs are making it virtually impossible for small farmers to survive. The globalization of non-sustainable industrial agriculture is evaporating the incomes of Third World farmers through a combination of devaluation of currencies, increase in costs of production and a collapse in commodity prices.

Economic globalization has been formed through last five centuries, during which more developed countries gain profits, influence and more economic lemons dominated some states and developed their trade, economic and productive activities. In recent years due technological progress and specially liberalization policies through the world, there has been more progress everywhere. Globalization, from the beginning, have conflicted national outlook and the national governments have seen it as a threat to their sovereignty. But it seems that the contemporary globalization trend is a factor in reduction of poverty phenomenon, and it has helped to some countries to be come more developed. Meanwhile there are some concerns also.

Neo liberal enthusiasts argue that globalization may well lead to more poverty in some cases, but they see this as a temporary situation which will rectify itself soon as the country's economy takes off on the road to industrialization. They also say that though poverty may well increase, the poor are getting less poor in relative terms globally. In other words the poor of today are more affluent than the poor of the past. Marxians say that globalization represents a race to bottom, with wages and social benefits declining and poverty increasing as a result of the triumph of capital over labor.

Globalization has encouraged economic growth through the spread of technology, investment and trade but this has reduced per capita income in least developed countries. Economic growth does help too reduce poverty but

it is more efficient in those countries where it is accompanied by government and anti-poverty measures. The impact of globalization on the improvement of living standards has been very uneven because of the freedom that it provides to private businesses to invest and de invest where it pleases. Thus improvements in living standards have been at their lowest in the least developed countries because there is less profit to be made from investing in them.

Behind the increasing interconnectedness promised by globalization are global decisions, policies, and practices. These are typically influenced, driven, or formulated by the rich and powerful. These can be leaders of rich countries or other global actors such as multinational corporations, institutions, and influential people. In the face of such enormous external influence, the governments of poor nations and their people are often powerless. As a result, in the global context, a few get wealthy while the majority struggle.

The poorest people will also have less access to health, education and other services. Problems of hunger, malnutrition and disease afflict the poorest in society. The poorest are also typically marginalized from society and have little representation or voice in public and political debates, making it even harder to escape poverty.

By contrast, the wealthier you are, the more likely you are to benefit from economic or political policies. The amount the world spends on military, financial bailouts and other areas that benefit the wealthy, compared to the amount spent to address the daily crisis of poverty and related problems are often staggering.

World income distribution continues to be very unequal and many poor countries particularly in Africa are stagnating. Moreover, there is much empirical evidence that openness contributes to more within-country inequality. China is a good example with coastal provinces as opposed to inland provinces reaping the major benefits of globalization.

On the one side it is argued that globalization improves living standards and reduces poverty through employment growth stimulated by increased trade and capital flows, the sharing of ideas, and the extension of democratic institutions. Macroeconomic stability, low inflation, and fiscal discipline are seen as imperatives for sustained economic growth and sustainable development. Globalization is perceived as the means for achieving international-development goals and for creating a more inclusive and equitable global economy.

On the other side it is argued that much of the world, especially the poorest countries, has been largely excluded from its benefits. Private investment flows are targeted to a minority of developing countries, bypassing poor countries because of their low human capital and perceived limited investment opportunities. The gap between rich and poor has tended to widen, inequalities have risen, debt has mounted promised debt relief under the enhanced Heavily Indebted Poor Country initiative has been slow in coming and trade subsidies, especially for agricultural produce, disproportionately benefit the North

However globalization is viewed, the reality of widespread poverty continues to linger. The HIV/AIDS pandemic is devastating economies, communities, and individual families, especially in the poorest countries; and it is widening inequalities within countries.

Poverty is multidimensional, as reflected in the international development goals and especially the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) . Without a more equitable distribution of the benefits of globalization both within

and between countries, it is unlikely that the development goals will be achieved by the target date of 2015 .

Globalization has direct effects on demographic processes. Those include movements of people within and across national borders, health and fertility outcomes, and changes in age structure. Urban populations will grow rapidly, posing challenges to sustainable development. The attainment of universal access to reproductive health that is, to gender-sensitive information and services is crucial for achieving the development goals. Access to reproductive-health services not only is directly related to health, social, and economic outcomes; it also enables individuals, particularly women, to exercise choice and opens opportunities. In sum, macroeconomic policies will need to be more carefully blended with social policies and protection measures to ensure that market forces do not neglect the needs of the poorest, and that poverty and inequality are not perpetuated. Put another way, globalization needs to be humanely managed and regulated. And there is a need for more developed countries to support the provision of global public goods and thereby contribute to national poverty-reduction strategies.

Globalization seems to be irreversible. It produces both winners and losers among the poor. Thus, the question that needs to be addressed is how we can better govern this process to make it more inclusive and fairer than the current conditions. That is, it is not globalization ought to be abandoned, but rather it is poor governance of globalization is what needs to be challenged. If managed correctly and fairly for the benefit of all, globalization could be a positive force. International community should act together in an effort to make available the resources necessary to wage a war against poverty and inequality .Naturally, this requires fundamental adjustment of the global status quo, starting with a true political pledge of the developing and developed countries to conceive an enhanced global financial and economic landscape.

Generally, it has been found that the poor are more likely to share in the gains from globalization when there are complementary policies in place, such as access to credit, technical know-how, and other complementary inputs. This can range from countries implementing minimum wage policies to protect unskilled workers who are most likely to be poor to encouraging export and incoming foreign investment, which has been linked to reduction in poverty levels in many countries .

There is also a need for a Global Collective Action to sustain a steady global economic expansion and reduce the likelihood of and contain the effects of global volatility as it is the poor countries that are known for its volatility. This international policy coordination should mobilize adequate and more effective aid for poverty reduction in order to eliminate debt of poor countries. It should provide for information and knowledge sharing, removes barriers to trade, provide preferential access to the poorest countries, provide increased international support in protecting global commons and combating global diseases.

Whatever the methods and measurements used, it is important that poverty reduction via economic growth becomes the ultimate aim of development endeavors towards a more peaceful, prosperous, and accountable economic world. It cannot be said that poverty can only be reduced if globalization effort is halted or vice-versa.

CONCLUSION

Many countries have made tremendous strides in reducing poverty but this will only be done if proper policies and strategies will be made so that the benefits on economic growth are equally distributed. Every phenomenon has pros and cons with it they should only be dealt properly. It is not proved that globalization directly leads

towards increase in poverty; it is just the mismanagement that increases poverty. Poverty is an issue which is prevailing from the past and it should be taken care of as it hinders the development of nations. Policies should be developed according to the state of countries. Developed countries need different policies and less developed countries need different policies. Economic growth should be monitored and it should increase the living standards of the all the population equally. The world has now become a global sphere. Decisions should be taken to compete successfully in this environment. Countries cannot be isolated from it. The poor countries which are struggling for their survival are also not able to take advantage from the rapid technological changes. The poor population is mostly uneducated and do not have the systems and skills to use them which is leading them further behind and other developed countries are fastly moving ahead. This is suppressing the less developed countries and increasing poverty further. The trade of these countries is also not well established and no investments take place here. All these negative effects of globalization on the less developed countries should be taken into account so that appropriate measures are taken to control them.

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